

Building the EU Cancer and Health Genomics Platform

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Deliverable information

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Deliverable number	5.5
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Objective of the deliverable

Contextualize and highlight a new tool which can be used across national and local health contexts to guide the implementation of remote/tele- genetic counselling.

Work performed

Context

As noted in our prior work (Deliverable 5.3¹), remote delivery or ‘telegenetics’ (*i.e. genetic counselling conducted via phone or video call*) can be a valuable tool for increasing access to genetic counselling in cancer, particularly for citizens living in rural areas. Several studies also demonstrate that remote genetic counselling is a more cost- and time-efficient delivery mode which does not compromise counselling uptake, quality, or patient satisfaction,²⁻⁶ leading to some calls for broader implementation of telegenetic counselling.⁷ These calls are tempered by the results of our prior work, as patient preference in the majority of Member States remains generally in favor of face-to-face delivery across pre- and post-test clinical scenarios (see Deliverable 5.4 for further details). Further, health professionals across multiple Member States noted reservations related to perceived reductions in quality in remote vs. face-to-face counselling; these reservations were particularly pronounced for complex clinical scenarios and the return of positive/significant test results, when telemedical consults are not geographically necessary, and where reimbursement for telemedical counselling is challenging or nonexistent (Deliverable 5.3).¹

The scope of its implementation notwithstanding, telegenetic counselling still has a significant role to play in counselling delivery across the EU – a majority of counselling consultations are estimated to be delivered remotely in 8 Member States, with a minority of counselling consultations delivered remotely in 17 further Member States.¹ Only in Luxembourg and Cyprus, where remote genetic counselling is not currently

legally permissible, is telegenetics completely absent from counselling delivery. Addressing barriers to genetic counselling in cancer through the recommendations presented in Deliverable 5.4 promises to increase access to and provision of genetic counselling across Europe, including both face-to-face and remote delivery modes. Accordingly, to guide implementation and enhancement of telegenetic counselling across multiple clinical and preventive applications, we introduce below a new framework of practical considerations which can help guide the integration of remote genetic counselling into both national and local health systems.

Practical Considerations for Remote Genetic Counselling Integration – *WHO Telehealth Quality of Care Tool*

In early 2024 (i.e. during the course of the CAN.HEAL project), the World Health Organization, European Region published the ‘Telehealth Quality of Care Tool,’ a framework for ensuring the implementation of telehealth services that provide high quality care.⁸ This includes but is not limited to telegenetic counselling. The development of this tool was very well-resourced, including inputs from four expert workshops and a subsequent presentation to representatives of multiple Member States. Further, the resulting framework is comprehensive, providing both recommendations and a self-assessment to facilitate the people centric, clinically effective, and safe implementation of telemedicine tailored to specific local and national contexts across the EU.

Accordingly, our planned activities related to the development of quality criteria and implementation guidance for telegenetics (*Deliverable 5.5, pre-amendment*) have been superseded by the development and publication of this well-resourced tool. We strongly recommend this tool for use across Member States. The telehealth self-

assessment tool and accompanying documents are freely available online at:

<https://www.who.int/europe/publications/i/item/WHO-EURO-2024-9475-49247-73556>

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